

Forecasting chlorophyll-a concentration in the North Sea

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Abstract. We present a machine learning approach to forecasting daily chlorophyll-a concentration in the North Sea from March to October using satellite-derived observations and reanalysis data from 2016 to 2020. The model employs extreme gradient boosting trees trained on a combination of oceanographic, biogeochemical, and meteorological predictors, including nutrient concentrations, sea surface temperature, and mixed layer depth. The forecast horizon spans up to seven days, with validation focusing on 2020 data. Performance metrics demonstrate the model's skill with a one-day forecast median absolute percentage deviation of 21.0%. Forecast errors increase with horizon length but maintain spatial and temporal stability. While the model outperforms naïve persistence benchmarks in most measures, the improvement is modest, reflecting the inherent complexity and variability of chlorophyll concentration dynamics. Such modest gains are expected given the challenging nature of forecasting biogeochemical ocean properties but nonetheless highlight the added value of incorporating a diverse set of oceanographic and meteorological predictors. Our approach leverages the synergy of Earth observation data and machine learning for improved short-term prediction of ocean biogeochemical conditions relevant to ecosystem health, fisheries management, and harmful algal bloom mitigation. The method addresses data sparsity challenges inherent to remote sensing by incorporating complementary reanalysis products and contributes towards sustainable ocean resource management and operational oceanography.

15 1 Introduction

Photosynthetic organisms in the sunlit upper layers of the ocean use chlorophyll to capture solar energy and produce organic matter, forming the foundation of marine food webs (Falkowski, 2012). In the long term, this activity transfers atmospheric carbon into the deep ocean, connecting carbon cycles between organic and inorganic stocks and shaping global climate trends. On shorter terms, fluctuations in ocean biogeochemistry affect marine ecosystems, human populations, and societies (Gruber, 2011). Chlorophyll production is sensitive to variations of nutrients, temperature, and physicochemical conditions like, e.g., ocean circulation and upwelling and mixed-layer dynamics and thus constitutes an indicator of the ocean's state (Behrenfeld et al., 2006; Falkowski and Oliver, 2007). Ocean chlorophyll influences water quality and fishery yields and drives the occurrence of harmful algal blooms (HAB) which demand timely and informed responses (Kudela et al., 2015). Forecasting ocean chlorophyll concentration for multiple days into the future would help protecting marine life, helps mitigating societal impacts, and helps establishing sustainable ocean resource management (Mills et al., 2013; Eveson et al., 2015). Initial methods for

modeling and forecasting weather and climate were developed about a century ago (Lynch, 2008). The physics of ocean and atmosphere systems is described by the Navier–Stokes equations and related differential equations that govern fluid flows and thermodynamics (Lacasse, 2020). Modeling of biogeochemistry like chlorophyll production relies on empirical relationships derived from laboratory experiments, biological theories and ecological principles (Cossarini et al., 2024). Different methods exist to couple physical and biogeochemical modeling and both satellite and in-situ observations are assimilated to reduce forecast biases (McWilliams, 2016; Holt et al., 2017; MacKinnon et al., 2017; Sharples et al., 2017; Fox-Kemper et al., 2019). But despite the increasing availability of observational data by deploying sensors (in-situ or space-borne) and significant advances in computational capabilities, the predictive ability did not increase in the last decades (Bauer et al., 2015). Examples of machine learning (ML) models which outperform Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) have emerged recently (Pathak et al., 2022; Bi et al., 2023; Nguyen et al., 2024; Price et al., 2024) and have been followed by examples of likewise approaches applied to ocean physics (Xiong et al., 2023) and Wang et al. (2024). Earth Observation (EO) data combined with supplemental information were used directly for ML-based forecasting of Earth’s surface reflectance Gao et al. (2023); Pellicer-Valero et al. (2024). Developing and demonstrating daily forecasts of remotely sensed chlorophyll concentration requires a daily Earth Observation chlorophyll concentration product. The OSPAR Commission provides state of the art product for the North Sea (OSPAR Commission, 2023). Spatiotemporal coverage of a daily satellite product is in principle incomplete and limited by cloud cover and satellite revisit cycles. Periods without satellite observation can comprise several days in the North Sea. Daily reanalysis, analysis and forecast data on ocean physics and biogeochemical parameters operationally supplied by the Copernicus Marine Service provide complete spatiotemporal coverage of the North Sea (E.U. Copernicus Marine Service Information, 2023b, a). Similarly, the Copernicus Climate Change Service provides daily weather reanalysis, analysis and forecasts (Hersbach et al., 2017). Daily reanalysis parameters are potential predictors of remotely sensed chlorophyll concentration, and machine learning facilitates exploring and exploiting their relations in a purely data-driven manner.

In this study, we pursue this idea and conduct an experiment. Our experiment considers the North Sea in the season from 01 March to 31 October in the years 2016–2020. The years 2016–2019 were used for training the forecast model while the year 2020 was considered for demonstration and validation. Table 1 lists all parameters included with the training dataset. Figure 1 illustrates the study area and depicts descriptive statistics of the observed chlorophyll concentration. We describe the transformation of source datasets into analysis-ready data cubes in Appendix A1 and formalize the forecast problem in Appendix A2. We considered several machine learning models developed or known for their application to time series forecasting problems: extreme gradient boosting (XGB) decision trees (Chen and Guestrin, 2016) and three recent transformer models (Lim et al., 2021; Gao et al., 2023; Grigsby et al., 2023). Eventually, we selected XGB trees because of their applicability to sparse data. We justify our selection in Appendix A3. We trained the XGB model with samples randomly selected from the training data cube. Training samples comprise the objective day and the history of the five preceding days without lateral or vertical context (Figure 2). We describe the forecast model and the training procedure in Appendix A4. In the remainder of this letter, we describe and discuss the results of our experiment. Eventually, we deduce conclusions and implications.

2 Results

60 Ocean color remote sensing studies suggest various metrics (Seegers et al., 2018) to evaluate performance which differ from metrics used in time series forecasting competitions (Makridakis et al., 2022a, b). We compute the bias, the coefficient of determination, the median absolute error (MAD), the median absolute percentage error (MAPD), the root mean squared error (RMSE), the root mean squared logarithmic error (RMSLE) which constitutes the training objective, and weighted root mean squared scaled error (WRMSSE). Appendix A5 explains the metrics. To validate the forecast model, we consider the season
65 from March to October in the year 2020. Metrics computed for training seasons (2016–2019) indicate the knowledge base of the forecast model. We display them for comparison only.

2.1 Total metrics

Figure 3 illustrates the distribution of forecasts of chlorophyll concentration versus observed chlorophyll concentration for a horizon of one day into the future. The dispersion of the distribution is symmetric along the identity line up to a magnitude of
70 about 10 mg m^{-3} . For higher concentrations, the forecast model underestimates the true value more likely. Figure 4 depicts the distribution of forecast errors for a horizon of one day. The magnitude of 75 percent of errors is less than 0.5 mg m^{-3} . The magnitude of 95 percent of errors is less than 1.5 mg m^{-3} . Similar diagrams for forecast horizons of multiple days (not illustrated) demonstrate that the dispersion of distributions increases with increasing horizon.

Table 2 summarizes metric scores achieved by the forecast model for horizons of 1–7 days into the future. For all horizons,
75 the magnitude of the bias is less than or equal to 0.15 mg m^{-3} and negligible compared to the objective of forecasting chlorophyll concentrations which are typical for algal blooms. The coefficient of determination is 0.75 for a horizon of one day. The MAD, MAPD, RMSE and RMSLE are 0.24 mg m^{-3} , 21.0, 1.24 mg m^{-3} and 0.22, respectively, for a forecast horizon of one day. The WRMSSE is 1.06 for a horizon of one day, which indicates that forecast errors are typically of the same magnitude as the variation of preceding observed concentrations of chlorophyll. All metric scores increase with increasing forecast horizon,
80 which indicates that errors from repeated application of the forecast model accumulate.

For comparison, Table 3 lists performance metrics scored by naïve, seasonal naïve, moving average (MA) and simple exponential smoothing (SES) benchmarks (Makridakis et al., 2022a, b) for a horizon of one day into the future and a history of up to five days into the past. The naïve benchmarks, persist a chlorophyll concentration observed on a preceding day into the forecast. The forecast model performs better than or equal to the naïve benchmarks in terms of the coefficient of determination,
85 MAPD, RMSE, and RMSLE. In terms of the bias, MAD and WRMSSE the naïve benchmarks perform better. MA and SES apply to a low proportion of samples only. The forecast model performs better than or equal to them in terms of most metrics. The WRMSSE of benchmarks is close unity as if observed values of chlorophyll concentration were varying randomly. Table 3 lists performance metrics obtained from reanalysis chlorophyll concentration, too (E.U. Copernicus Marine Service Information, 2023a). The reanalysis exhibits a high bias and the lowest metric scores.

90 2.2 Projected metrics

Figure 5 maps the RMSE of forecasts of chlorophyll concentrations made for horizons of one, four, and seven days into the future. The RMSE is higher than 1.5 mg m^{-3} in the plume of the River Thames and very near to the coast only. For comparison, Figure 6 maps the RMSLE of forecasts of chlorophyll concentrations for the same horizons. Minimizing the RMSLE for a horizon of one day into the future was the objective of the training. The RMSLE exhibits less contrast between coastal and open sea than the RMSE, which demonstrates a relatively balanced performance of the forecast model with respect to its objective. Figures reffig:07 and 8 show time series of the RMSE for horizons of one and seven days, respectively. The RMSE is typically less than 1.0 mg m^{-3} but can reach up to 3 mg m^{-3} in April, when algal blooms occur. Time series of the RMSLE (not illustrated) exhibit less variation, which again indicates a relatively balanced performance. The RMSE increases with increasing forecast horizon, but geographic and temporal patterns remain relatively stable.

100 2.3 Example cases

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2.4 Video analysis

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displays a pronounced bloom in the Northwest, triggered by its visibility the day before. Figure 19 displays March 25. The algal bloom in the Northwest is visible but has diminished. The one-day and two-day forecasts still indicate a more pronounced bloom.

125 3 Summary and discussion

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135 The forecast model considers some predictors more relevant than others. Figures 20 and 21 show the importance of the most relevant predictors. Figure 20 ranks feature importance in terms of the total gain, which designates the total contribution of a feature to the final terms of the objective function used to train the forecast model. Figure 21 ranks feature importance in terms of the total cover, which designates the total number of decisions which were associated with a feature when the trained model was applied to the training dataset.

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4 Conclusions

We pursued the idea of time series forecasting of remotely sensed chlorophyll concentration in the North Sea in an experiment.
175 Within this experiment, we trained a forecast model with observational data of chlorophyll concentration, ocean physics and biogeochemistry reanalysis, and weather reanalysis. Training data were acquired for the season from March 01 to October 31 within the years 2016–2019. When applied to the same season in the year 2020, the trained forecast model performs better than naïve persistence benchmarks, which is not a natural course of action. Our results demonstrate that the trained forecast model learned more than persistence. Mathematically, the forecast model constitutes a multivariate piecewise constant
180 function which has learned the mean of the statistical distribution of chlorophyll concentration values in predictor space. The model considers the relevant temporal dynamics, which comprise five days, and explains which predictors are most important: preceding observations of chlorophyll concentration, mole concentration of nutrients in sea water, bathymetry, ocean mixed layer thickness, mean dynamic topography, sea water salinity, and sea water acidity.

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Code and data availability. Forecast model code (<https://bcdev.github.io/fcwq-wqf/>) is publicly available under MIT License. Data cubes for training and validating a forecast model (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14932066>) are published under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

195 *Video supplement.* A video supplement (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14930798>) compares observed and modeled chlorophyll concentration to forecasts of chlorophyll concentration for several days into the future. The video and its individual frames are published under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

Appendix A: Materials and methods

A1 Data cubes

200 A data cube was generated for training and validating the forecast model, which covers the North Sea from 1.0 °E to 10.0 °E and 50 °N to 58 °N and the season March–October of the years 2016–2020. Technically, a data cube comprises multidimensional data arrays, each of which represents values of a single parameter. Table 1 lists the parameters included with the training data cube. Gridded data of observed chlorophyll concentration in sea water were downloaded from OSPAR Commission (2023) at a spatial resolution of 1 km. Gridded reanalysis data of biogeochemical and ocean physics parameters were acquired from
205 E.U. Copernicus Marine Service Information (2023a, b) and bi-cubically interpolated to the grid of observed chlorophyll concentration. Logically, all data arrays share the same spatiotemporal coordinate dimensions (i.e., time, latitude, longitude). Some data arrays share an additional depth coordinate dimension (viz. Table 1). A supplemental data cube of reanalysis chlorophyll concentration (E.U. Copernicus Marine Service Information, 2023a) was generated for benchmarking (viz. Table 3). Eventually, the trained forecast model was used to generate data cubes of chlorophyll concentration forecast for horizons of 1–7 days.
210 Generated data cubes and a supplemental video are published (Quast et al., 2025a, b).

A2 Problem formulation

Let $x_{\{w\}}[t_i]$ denote observed values of chlorophyll concentration at time step t_i , and let $x_{\{a\}}[t_i]$ denote the values of associated meteorological, biogeochemical and ocean physics predictors. We denote the values of predictors involved with the forecasting problem by $x_{\{w,a\}}$ without referring to a specific instant and by $x_{\{w,a\}}[t_i]$ when we refer to a specific time step. We further refer

215 to a sequence of multiple consecutive time steps by $[t_j, t_{j+1}, t_{j+2}, \dots]$. For example, $[t_{i-1}, \dots, t_{i-m}]$ denote m consecutive
time steps preceding a time step t_i . We expect that observed values $x_{\{w\}}$ are sparsely available (e.g., due to cloud cover and
satellite revisit cycles) but presume that predictor values $x_{\{a\}}$ are usually available in terms of reanalysis, analysis or forecast.

Let $\hat{x}_{\{w\}}[t_i]$ denote a forecast, which corresponds to the observed value $x_{\{w\}}[t_i]$. Let the forecast be made at time step t_{i-1}
when values $x_{\{w,a\}}[t_{i-1}, \dots, t_{i-m}]$ and forecasts of covariates $\hat{x}_{\{a\}}[t_i]$ are known. Then the problem of forecasting chlorophyll
220 concentration consists of finding a forecast model

$$f(\hat{x}_{\{a\}}[t_i], x_{\{w,a\}}[t_{i-1}, \dots, t_{i-m}]) = \hat{x}_{\{w\}}[t_i], \quad (\text{A1})$$

which minimizes squared logarithmic error terms

$$L(\hat{x}_{\{w\}}, x_{\{w\}}) = \frac{1}{2} (\ln(1 + \hat{x}_{\{w\}}/(1 \text{ mg m}^{-3})) - \ln(1 + x_{\{w\}}/(1 \text{ mg m}^{-3})))^2. \quad (\text{A2})$$

The squared logarithmic error objective penalizes the squared absolute forecast error for lower concentrations of chlorophyll
225 $x_{\{w\}} \ll 1 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$ and the squared relative error for higher concentrations $x_{\{w\}} \gg 1 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$, which results in a penalty
which is qualitatively consistent with the uncertainty of observed chlorophyll concentrations. Since observations $x_{\{w\}}$ will be
sparse, we require that f is able to yield a forecast $\hat{x}_{\{w\}}$ based on predictors $\hat{x}_{\{a\}}$ and $x_{\{a\}}$ only.

If the above forecasting problem is solved, the problem of forecasting multiple time steps, i.e., of obtaining forecasts
 $\hat{x}_{\{w\}}[t_i, \dots, t_{i+h}]$ with a horizon of h additional time steps ahead of t_i is solved by recurrent application of f :

$$230 \quad \hat{x}_{\{w\}}[t_i] = f(\hat{x}_{\{a\}}[t_i], x_{\{w,a\}}[t_{i-1}, \dots, t_{i-m}]) \quad (\text{A3})$$

$$\hat{x}_{\{w\}}[t_{i+1}] = f(\hat{x}_{\{a\}}[t_{i+1}], \hat{x}_{\{w,a\}}[t_i], x_{\{w,a\}}[t_{i-1}, \dots, t_{i-m+1}]) \quad (\text{A4})$$

...

$$\hat{x}_{\{w\}}[t_{i+h}] = f(\hat{x}_{\{a\}}[t_{i+h}], \hat{x}_{\{w,a\}}[t_i, \dots, t_{i+h-1}], x_{\{w,a\}}[t_{i-1}, \dots, t_{i-m+h}]). \quad (\text{A5})$$

The mathematical formulation of the forecast problem determines the basic sampling strategy used for the training of the
235 forecast model, which is illustrated in Figure A1. For n randomly drawn locations of interest enumerated by k , we collect
values $x_{\{a\}}^k[t_i]$ for randomly drawn time steps t_i and values $x_{\{w,a\}}^k[t_{i-1}, \dots, t_{i-m}]$ for m consecutive time steps preceding
 t_i . These features are the predictors that constitute the input to the forecast model. Observed values $x_{\{w\}}^k[t_i]$ of chlorophyll
concentration constitute the expected output of the forecast model. If the observed value is unavailable, the sample at location
 k for time step t_i is not included with the set of training samples. Embedding time information, like the day of the year or
240 (if anthropogenic factors are important) the day of the week, is essential. Time information is a predictor which we formally
subsume under the index a . Table 1 lists the predictors x_w, x_a with $w \in \{0\}$ and $a \in \{1, \dots, 19\}$. Our sampling strategy does
not consider the lateral vicinity of the locations of interest. Values of chlorophyll concentration and of covariates within the
lateral vicinity of a location of interest, however, may formally be enumerated by indices w and a , too.

A3 Model selection

245 Long short-term memory (LSTM) networks are a type of recurrent neural network capable of learning from multivariate time series and of capturing complex relationships between covariates (Martinuzzi et al., 2023, e.g.). The Temporal Fusion Transformer (TFT) leverages LSTM networks and transformer models (Vaswani et al., 2017) with respect to the problem of multivariate time series forecasting (Lim et al., 2021). The TFT exhibits an explicit notion of time dependent and independent predictors (Lim et al., 2021). The Spacetimeformer (Grigsby et al., 2023) and Earthformer (Gao et al., 2023) extend transform-
250 ers with the capability of time series forecasting and exhibit an explicit notion of space, too. Extreme gradient boosting (XGB) trees (Chen and Guestrin, 2016) are a generally applicable type of machine learning model which have won recent time series forecasting competitions (Januschowski et al., 2022; Makridakis et al., 2022a, b).

Based on original literature (Chen and Guestrin, 2016; Lim et al., 2021; Grigsby et al., 2023; Gao et al., 2023), Table A1 compares the capabilities of transformers and XGB trees in aspects we considered relevant for chlorophyll concentration time
255 series forecasting. Transformers are capable of learning from and processing occasionally missing predictor data but if data are sparse, imputation is the better practice. XGB models are explicitly capable of learning from and processing sparse data. Transformers incorporate attention mechanisms (Vaswani et al., 2017) which extract the most important features and help explaining predictions. The XGB software (Chen and Guestrin, 2016) includes functions to analyze the importance of features used by a model, which helps interpretation. Using quantile regression, both TFT and XGB models are capable of quantifying
260 uncertainty of predictions in terms of prediction intervals. The TFT is the only model, which has an explicit notion of future and past to present predictors and static predictors. XGB trees learn spatiotemporal semantics implicitly within their training. Due to their ability to learn from sparse observations of chlorophyll concentration, we eventually selected XGB trees to tackle the forecasting problem.

A4 Model training

265 Gradient boosting is an ensemble method that builds decision trees (termed weak learners) sequentially, each learner attempting to correct the errors of its predecessor (Friedman, 2001). Eventually, the ensemble of trees approximates the relation between predictors and the target by a multivariate step function. Figure A1 illustrates the concept. The initial weak learner f_1 is trained to predict the target y with residual errors ε_1 . Each subsequent weak learner f_i is trained to predict the (negative of) the errors of the preceding learner, $-\varepsilon_{i-1}$, with residual errors ε_i such that the magnitude of errors ε_i is less than the magnitude of errors
270 ε_{i-1} . Eventually, after k iterations, the sum of weak learners

$$\sum_{i=1}^k f_i(x) = y + \varepsilon_k \tag{A6}$$

approximates the target y with acceptable errors ε_k . Extreme gradient boosting (XGB) is a refined boosting method, which uses Newton's method instead of simple gradient descent steps to minimize the objective function (Chen and Guestrin, 2016). We trained the XGB model on the data for the seasons 2016–2019 and used the data for 2020 for validation. The iterative training
275 was stopped when the squared logarithmic error objective stopped decreasing for the validation dataset. We considered different

training histories of 1–14 days. Histories longer than five days, however, did not improve the training results. All training experiments were carried out with default hyperparameter values.

A5 Validation metrics

We evaluated the performance of the trained forecast model by computing certain metrics which characterize the forecast errors. Let $i \in \mathbb{I}$ enumerate samples of chlorophyll concentration. Let $x_{t_i,i}$ denote the value of chlorophyll concentration observed at time t_i and let $\hat{x}_{t_i,i}$ denote the corresponding forecast. Let $X = |\mathbb{I}|^{-1} \sum_{i \in \mathbb{I}} x_{t_i,i}$ be the mean observed chlorophyll concentration, and let $\hat{X} = |\mathbb{I}|^{-1} \sum_{i \in \mathbb{I}} \hat{x}_{t_i,i}$ be the mean forecast. Then we compute the bias

$$\text{bias}(\hat{x}, x) = \hat{X} - X, \quad (\text{A7})$$

the coefficient of determination

$$r^2(\hat{x}, x) = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i \in \mathbb{I}} (\hat{x}_{t_i,i} - x_{t_i,i})^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathbb{I}} (x_{t_i,i} - X)^2}, \quad (\text{A8})$$

the median absolute deviation (MAD)

$$\text{mad}(\hat{x}, x) = \text{median}_{i \in \mathbb{I}} |\hat{x}_{t_i,i} - x_{t_i,i}|, \quad (\text{A9})$$

the median absolute percentage deviation (MAPD)

$$\text{mapd}(\hat{x}, x) = 100 \text{ median}_{i \in \mathbb{I}^1} \frac{|\hat{x}_{t_i,i} - x_{t_i,i}|}{x_{t_i,i}}, \quad \mathbb{I}^1 = \{i \in \mathbb{I} | x_{t_i,i} \geq 1.0 \text{ mg m}^{-3}\}, \quad (\text{A10})$$

the root mean squared error (RMSE)

$$\text{rmse}(\hat{x}, x) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{|\mathbb{I}|} \sum_{i \in \mathbb{I}} (\hat{x}_{t_i,i} - x_{t_i,i})^2}, \quad (\text{A11})$$

and the root mean squared logarithmic error (RMSLE)

$$\text{rmsle}(\hat{x}, x) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{|\mathbb{I}|} \sum_{i \in \mathbb{I}} (\ln(1 + \hat{x}_{t_i,i}/(1 \text{ mg m}^{-3})) - \ln(1 + x_{t_i,i}/(1 \text{ mg m}^{-3})))^2}. \quad (\text{A12})$$

For $x \ll 1 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$ and $x \gg 1 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$ the RMSLE asymptotically approaches the RMSE and the MAPD, respectively. Time series forecasting competitions define the root mean squared scaled error (RMSSE) which scales the RMSE with the root mean squared difference of preceding observed values (Makridakis et al., 2022a, b). For each sample $x_{t_j,j}$ where b preceding observations $x_{t_{j-1},j}, \dots, x_{t_{j-b},j}$ and $h - 1$ subsequent observations $x_{t_{j+1},j}, \dots, x_{t_{j+h},j}$ exist, the RMSSE is

$$\text{rmsse}(\hat{x}_j, x_j) = \sqrt{\frac{\frac{\sum_{k=0}^{h-1} (\hat{x}_{t_{j+k},j} - x_{t_{j+k},j})^2}{h}}{\frac{\sum_{k=1}^{b-1} (x_{t_{j-k},j} - x_{t_{j-k-1},j})^2}{b-1}}}. \quad (\text{A13})$$

Figure A1. Schematic illustration of the training of a gradient boosting model. Classification and regression tree (CART) weak learners f are added successively to minimize residual errors ε .

Table A1. Comparison of candidate machine learning models

Aspect	TFT	Spacetimeformer	Earthformer	XGB
Data, sparse	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	explicit
Prediction, explainability	explicit	explicit	explicit	explicit
Prediction, uncertainty	explicit	n.a.	n.a.	explicit
Predictor, future	explicit	n.a.	n.a.	implicit
Predictor, past to present	explicit	explicit	explicit	implicit
Predictor, static	explicit	n.a.	n.a.	implicit

We evaluate the RMSSE for a horizon of $h = 1$ and a history of $b = 5$. Let $\mathbb{J} \subseteq \mathbb{I}$ denote the set of all samples where the RMSSE
300 can be evaluated. Then we compute the weighted root mean squared error (WRMSSE) with equal weights

$$\text{wrmsse}(\hat{x}, x) = \frac{1}{|\mathbb{J}|} \sum_{j \in \mathbb{J}} \text{rmsse}(\hat{x}_j, x_j). \quad (\text{A14})$$

For time series which varies randomly a WRMSSE of 1.0 is expected. Metrics where evaluated in total, i.e., \mathbb{I} comprises all samples, projected laterally, i.e., \mathbb{I} comprises all time steps for each objective location, and projected temporally, i.e., \mathbb{I} comprises all locations for each objective time step.

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Figure 1. Descriptive statistics of observed chlorophyll concentration (OSPAR Commission, 2023) in the North Sea for the validation season (2020) and the training seasons (2016–2019). Allan deviation (or two-sample deviation) indicates the day-to-day fluctuation.

Figure 2. Schematic illustration of the spatiotemporal structure a training sample with predictor values and an observed value of chlorophyll concentration for an objective day i and predictor values (including values of chlorophyll concentration, if observed) for the five preceding days.

Figure 3. Distribution of forecasts of chlorophyll concentration versus observed chlorophyll concentration for a horizon of one day into the future. The dispersion of the distribution increases with increasing horizon.

Figure 4. Distribution of errors of forecasts of chlorophyll concentration for a horizon of one day into the future. The dispersion of the distribution increases with increasing horizon.

Figure 5. Root mean squared error (RMSE) of forecasts of chlorophyll concentration for horizons of one, four, and seven days into the future.

Figure 6. Root mean squared logarithmic error (RMSLE) of forecasts of chlorophyll concentration for horizons of one, four, and seven days into the future. Minimizing the total RMSLE of the one-day forecast (2016–2019) was the training objective.

Figure 7. Time series of the root mean squared error (RMSE) of forecasts of chlorophyll concentration for a horizon of one day into the future.

Figure 8. Time series of root mean squared error (RMSE) of forecasts of chlorophyll concentration for a horizon of seven days into the future.

Figure 9. Number of satellite observations (2020) and location of example cases.

Figure 10. Example of a time series of observed chlorophyll concentration and corresponding forecasts for horizons of 1–7 days into the future (Skagerrak). The time series considers a single pixel.

Figure 11. Example of a time series of observed chlorophyll concentration and corresponding forecasts for horizons of 1–7 days into the future (German Bight). The time series considers a single pixel.

Figure 12. Example of a time series of observed chlorophyll concentration and corresponding forecasts for horizons of 1–7 days into the future (Southern Bight). The time series considers a single pixel.

Figure 13. Example of a time series of observed chlorophyll concentration and corresponding forecasts for horizons of 1–7 days into the future (Skagerrak). The time series considers a rectangular area, the pixels of which are lined up for visualization.

Figure 14. Example of a time series of observed chlorophyll concentration and corresponding forecasts for horizons of 1–7 days into the future (German Bight). The time series considers a rectangular area, the pixels of which are lined up for visualization.

Figure 15. Example of a time series of observed chlorophyll concentration and corresponding forecasts for horizons of 1–7 days into the future (Southern Bight). The time series considers a rectangular area, the pixels of which are lined up for visualization.

Figure 16. Example of observed and reanalysis chlorophyll concentration (OSPAR Commission, 2023; E.U. Copernicus Marine Service Information, 2023a) compared to forecasts of chlorophyll concentration for horizons of 1–6 days into the future (2017-03-22). Missing observations are usually due to clouds. Observations and forecasts were convolved with a Gaussian filter of full width at half maximum corresponding to the spatial resolution of the reanalysis (7 km) to facilitate visual comparison. Similar displays are available for all days in the March to October season in 2017–2020 (Quast et al., 2025a, b).

Figure 17. Example of observed and reanalysis chlorophyll concentration compared to forecasts of chlorophyll concentration. Like Figure 16 but one day later (2017-03-23). The sudden algal bloom observed in the Northwest is not visible in the forecasts and the reanalysis.

Figure 18. Example of observed and reanalysis chlorophyll concentration compared to forecasts of chlorophyll concentration. Like Figure 17 but one day later (2017-03-24). The algal bloom which was observed in the Northwest the day before is hidden by clouds. It is visible in the one-day forecast but not in the reanalysis.

Figure 19. Example of observed and reanalysis chlorophyll concentration compared to forecasts of chlorophyll concentration. Like Figure 18 but one day later (2017-03-25). The algal bloom which was observed in the Northwest two days before has diminished. The bloom was visible in the one-day forecast for the day before and is now visible in the two-day forecast, too.

Figure 20. The twelve most important predictors ranked by total gain. The total gain designates the contribution of a predictor to the final training objective.

Figure 21. The twelve most important predictors ranked by total cover. The total cover designates the total number of training decisions associated with a predictor.

Table 1. List of predictors used to train the forecast model. Mnemonic names identify parameters included with source datasets (OSPAR Commission, 2023; E.U. Copernicus Marine Service Information, 2023a, b; Hersbach et al., 2017). Most important parameters are underlined. Depth, if applicable, designates the vertical depth level considered. Symbols indicate how we refer to a parameter formally. Parameters without explicit time steps constitute static information.

Parameter (mnemonic name)	depth	unit	symbol	time steps
<u>Chlorophyll concentration in sea water (chl)</u>		mg m ⁻³	x_0	t_{i-1}, \dots, t_{i-5}
<u>Sea floor depth below geoid (deptho)</u>		m	x_1	
<u>Day of year (doy)</u>			x_2	$t_i, t_{i-1}, \dots, t_{i-5}$
<u>Sea surface height above geoid (mdt)</u>		m	x_3	
<u>Ocean mixed layer thickness (mlotst)</u>		m	x_4	$t_i, t_{i-1}, \dots, t_{i-5}$
<u>Mole concentration of nitrate in sea water (no3)</u>	3.0 m	mmol m ⁻³	x_5	$t_i, t_{i-1}, \dots, t_{i-5}$
Mole concentration of dissolved oxygen in sea water (o2)	3.0 m	mmol m ⁻³	x_6	$t_i, t_{i-1}, \dots, t_{i-5}$
<u>Sea water ph reported on total scale (ph)</u>	3.0 m		x_7	$t_i, t_{i-1}, \dots, t_{i-5}$
Mole concentration of phosphate in sea water (po4)	3.0 m	mmol m ⁻³	x_8	$t_i, t_{i-1}, \dots, t_{i-5}$
<u>Sea water salinity (so)</u>	3.0 m	10 ⁻³	x_9	$t_i, t_{i-1}, \dots, t_{i-5}$
Surface downwelling shortwave flux in air (ssrd)		J m ⁻²	x_{10}	$t_i, t_{i-1}, \dots, t_{i-5}$
Sea surface temperature (sst)		K	x_{11}	$t_i, t_{i-1}, \dots, t_{i-5}$
Total cloud cover (tcc)			x_{12}	$t_i, t_{i-1}, \dots, t_{i-5}$
Sea water potential temperature (thetao)	3.0 m	° C	x_{13}	$t_i, t_{i-1}, \dots, t_{i-5}$
Total precipitation (tp)		m	x_{14}	$t_i, t_{i-1}, \dots, t_{i-5}$
10 metre U wind component (u10)		m s ⁻¹	x_{15}	$t_i, t_{i-1}, \dots, t_{i-5}$
Eastward sea water velocity (uo)	3.0 m	m s ⁻¹	x_{16}	$t_i, t_{i-1}, \dots, t_{i-5}$
10 metre V wind component (v10)		m s ⁻¹	x_{17}	$t_i, t_{i-1}, \dots, t_{i-5}$
Northward sea water velocity (vo)	3.0 m	m s ⁻¹	x_{18}	$t_i, t_{i-1}, \dots, t_{i-5}$
Sea surface height above geoid (zos)		m	x_{19}	$t_i, t_{i-1}, \dots, t_{i-5}$

Table 2. Summary of forecast model performance metrics for the validation season 2020 (10,442,908 samples). Numbers in parentheses designate corresponding metrics for the training seasons 2016–2019 (39,665,746 samples).

Horizon (days)	bias (mg m ⁻³)	coeff. of det.	MAD (mg m ⁻³)	MAPD	RMSE (mg m ⁻³)	RMSLE	WRMSSE
1	-0.09 (-0.15)	0.75 (0.67)	0.24 (0.18)	21.0 (19.0)	1.24 (1.57)	0.22 (0.21)	1.06 (1.21)
2	-0.11 (-0.17)	0.71 (0.64)	0.27 (0.21)	24.0 (22.0)	1.33 (1.65)	0.24 (0.23)	1.26 (1.53)
3	-0.14 (-0.19)	0.68 (0.61)	0.29 (0.23)	26.0 (25.0)	1.40 (1.70)	0.26 (0.25)	1.43 (1.76)
4	-0.15 (-0.20)	0.66 (0.60)	0.31 (0.24)	27.0 (26.0)	1.45 (1.73)	0.28 (0.26)	1.52 (1.94)
5	-0.15 (-0.21)	0.64 (0.59)	0.32 (0.25)	29.0 (27.0)	1.50 (1.75)	0.29 (0.26)	1.58 (2.10)
6	-0.15 (-0.21)	0.62 (0.58)	0.34 (0.26)	30.0 (28.0)	1.53 (1.77)	0.30 (0.27)	1.75 (2.49)
7	-0.14 (-0.21)	0.61 (0.58)	0.34 (0.27)	30.0 (29.0)	1.54 (1.78)	0.30 (0.28)	1.81 (2.69)

Table 3. Summary of benchmark and reanalysis performance metrics for the validation season 2020. All benchmarks consider a horizon of one day into the future. Benchmark samples require a history of 1–5 preceding observations. Numbers in parentheses designate forecast model performance metrics evaluated on the benchmark samples.

Benchmark	bias (mg m^{-3})	coeff. of det.	MAD (mg m^{-3})	MAPD	RMSE (mg m^{-3})	RMSLE	WRMSSE	samples
Naïve	0.02 (−0.06)	0.81 (0.82)	0.19 (0.20)	18.0 (18.0)	1.09 (1.04)	0.19 (0.18)	1.03 (1.06)	5,395,014
S. naïve	0.01 (−0.08)	0.75 (0.77)	0.21 (0.23)	21.0 (20.0)	1.25 (1.18)	0.22 (0.21)	1.03 (1.06)	9,244,171
MA	0.02 (−0.06)	0.76 (0.82)	0.39 (0.27)	23.0 (19.0)	1.23 (1.06)	0.27 (0.20)	1.29 (1.06)	553,005
SES	0.02 (−0.06)	0.82 (0.82)	0.27 (0.27)	19.0 (19.0)	1.07 (1.06)	0.21 (0.20)	1.02 (1.06)	553,005
Reanalysis	−1.20 (−0.09)	0.00 (0.75)	0.45 (0.24)	64.0 (20.0)	2.56 (1.25)	0.56 (0.22)	2.24 (1.06)	10,231,894